

Health Monitoring System for the ICARUS inflatable heat shield Aerodemonstrator

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Abstract

ICARUS is a project funded by the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE programme under the grant agreement #101134997. It targets to bring up to TRL6 the maturation of Inflatable Heat Shields (IHS).

This paper will present the concept of the Health Monitoring System (HMS) for the ICARUS Inflatable Heat Shield Aerodemonstrator. The HMS will oversee the thermal, structural, and dynamic state of the re-entry vehicle; these data will be sent via telemetry as well as gather on-board by a modular and flight-proven Data Acquisition and Storage System. Most of the data will be stored on crash resistant data storage modules. A major goal of the HMS will be to demonstrate the technology maturation for the innovative flexible-electronics-based and fibre-optic-based sensors. The HMS will also include Flush Air Data System to analyse the aerodynamic behaviour vehicle, and Digital Image Correlation System to investigate the interaction between the flow field and the IHS.

Keywords: *Inflatable Heat Shields, Re-entry Technologies, Aerodynamic Decelerators, Health Monitoring System, Fibre-optic Sensors, Flexible Electronics, Flush Air Data System, Digital Image Correlation*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, there has been an increase in interest in inflatable structures for space vehicle re-entry. NASA has successfully demonstrated this technology with the series of projects and flight experiments, beginning with *Inflatable Re-entry Vehicle Experiment* (IRVE) [1], a capsule with a mushroom-shaped Inflatable Heat Shield (IHS); this sparked further research into this technology, with the projects *Hypersonic Inflatable Aerodynamic Decelerator* (HIAD) [2] and *Low-Earth Orbit Flight Test of an Inflatable Decelerator* (LOFTID) [3]. Amongst other long-lasting undertakings in this field, there have been JAXA's *Membrane*

Aeroshell for Atmospheric-entry Capsule (MAAC) [4, 5]; *European Flexible hEat Shields advanced TPS design and tests for future in-Orbit demonstration* (EFESTO) by a European consortium composed of Deimos Space, CIRA, ONERA, DLR, Aviospace, and Politecnico di Torino [6, 7]; and *Mini-Irene* by CIRA [8].

Whenever a project was concluded with a flight test, be it ballistic or an actual re-entry, the capsule was equipped with a suite of instrumentation, providing valuable data for the post-flight analysis (PFA) and verification of the design assumptions and models. IRVE-1 and IRVE-2 vehicles both contained a device called Sub-A, which in turn consisted of an integral three-axis accelerometer, a ring accelerometer, a magnetometer, and four external slit sensors, in order to measure its position, attitude, and acceleration. There were also video cameras, which provided not only flight documentation, but also photogrammetric analysis of the motion of the inflatable aeroshell. Moreover, a set of thermocouples was employed to measure the temperature of the IHS at various points and layers. Finally, pressure transducers were used for internal gas pressure measurements. [2, 9]

IRVE-3 expanded the sensor suite of the previous projects with additional pressure transducers, thermocouples, heat flux gauges, thermistors and an inertial measurement unit (IMU) [10, 11]. LOFTID employed an even more extensive set of sensors, totalling over 150 various instruments; amongst them were: thermocouples, total heat flux sensors, pressure transducers, a radiometer, an IMU, a GPS module, Flush Air Data System (FADS), load cells, and cameras (both visual-spectrum and infrared) at the vehicle's aft [12].

Mini-Irene, another successful flight experiment, was developed by CIRA and demonstrated a flexible deployable (not inflatable) heat shield. Its sensor suite consisted of a GPS module and accelerometers for position and attitude monitoring, in order to analyse the capsule flight dynamics in the PFA; and cameras in the aft region to register the flight and behaviour of the heat shield. The

data from the GPS and the accelerometers were sent down via telemetry. [8]

This paper describes the Health Monitoring System (HMS) of the project **ICARUS**, which stands for *Inflatable Concept Aeroshell for the Recovery of a re-Usable launcher Stage*. The project aims at further investigation of the Inflatable Heat Shield technology. ICARUS is a project funded by the European Union’s HORIZON EUROPE program, under the grant agreement #101134997; it is a follow-up project of EFESTO and EFESTO-2, with the goal to design, manufacture, and a flight test of a technology demonstrator for inflatable re-entry vehicles, thus increasing their maturity level in Europe to TRL 6. The HMS is developed by three partners:

- DLR Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology, Department of Supersonic and Hypersonic Technologies
- Pangaia Grado Zero SRL
- Demcon High-Tech Systems Delft BV.

In its baseline, the Aerodemonstrator of an IHS will be flight-tested through a sub-orbital flight executed by a sounding rocket launched from ES-RANGE and managed by DLR-MORABA. [13]

In order to obtain valuable flight data from the experiment, a suite of measurement and recording instruments has been conceptualised and is currently in preliminary design stage. The data will be transmitted via telemetry to provide a real-time monitoring of the vehicle’s state; the data will also be saved locally to DLR in-house flight-proven impact-resistant data storage units. The sensors, data acquisition and storage modules as well as power distribution units all constitute the Health Monitoring System of ICARUS.

2. HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The Health Monitoring System of ICARUS will consist of sensors of various types, measuring quantities that have been identified as scientifically interesting or crucial to the mission success, in different regions of the vehicles. Thus, the HMS serves several purposes:

- to oversee the thermal, structural and dynamic state of the vehicle
- to provide the experiment with valuable scientific data for PFA
- to test innovative sensors in flight.

The HMS sensors will use various measurement and integration techniques, therefore it is developed by three partners: DLR, responsible for conventional sensors such as pressure transducers, thermocouples, coaxial thermocouples, etc. as well as for

the cameras, data acquisition and storage systems, and work package coordination; Demcon, developing innovative fiber-optical sensors to be used in the Inflatable Heat Shield; and PGZ, responsible for innovative flexible electronics and textile-mounted sensors.

2.1. Health Monitoring System measurement areas

The positioning concept for the sensors has been developed according to the objectives of the HMS and the whole project, and aided by engineering experience coming from previous studies like EFESTO and EFESTO-2 as well as CFD simulations performed by ONERA [14], depicted in Fig. 1. Thus, several scientifically interesting or thermally/structurally crucial regions have been identified; they are depicted in Fig. 2. The measurement regions, monitored physical quantities, and reasoning behind the choice are listed in Tab. 1.

Figure 1. CFD performed by ONERA [14]

Figure 2. Designated measurement areas

At this point, it is crucial in the context of the HMS and the whole experiment to underline the difference between the Inflatable Structure (IS), the

Table 1. Measurement areas and quantities

Region	Quantities	Reasoning
rigid steel tip	pressure, temperature, heat flux	highest thermal and mechanical loads
outer frontside of IHS	pressure, temperature	flow conditions onto the IHS
inner frontside of IHS	temperature, strain	load-carrying part of the IHS
cylinder surface	pressure, temperature, heat flux, strain	aerodynamics in the recirculation zone
internal structure	temperature, acceleration, vibrations	load-carrying part of the cylinder
outer backside of IHS	temperature, deformation (s. cameras)	inflation monitoring, DIC
inner backside of IHS	temperature, strain	correlation with the camera readings
cold gas generator	pressure, temperature	crucial system
camera pedestal	visible (VIS) and infrared (IR) spectra	Digital Image Correlation

Flexible Thermal Protection System (FTPS), and the Inflatable Heat Shield (IHS):

- The Inflatable Structure carries the mechanical loads; in the consortium it is developed by ATMOS [15].
- The Flexible Thermal Protection System insulates the IS from the aerothermal loads from the inflow; it is developed by CIRA [16].
- Both parts together build the Inflatable Heat Shield.

2.2. Sensor positioning

More detailed concept of the sensor positioning on the frontshell of the capsule is depicted in Fig. 3; the cross-section of the IHS, shown in Fig. 4, explains the suggested exact locations of the sensors. Fig. 5 depicts the sensor positioning inside and on the surface of the primary structure cylinder, and at the backshell. This positioning is derived from the aforementioned identified quantities to measure.

2.2.1. Capsule windward side

The pressure sensors at the rigid steel tip constitute a crucial part of the frontshell instrumentation; their readings shall be utilised for the Flush Air Data System of the Aerodemonstrator. FADS utilises several pressure orifices at the nose of an object to determine angle of attack, angle of sideslip, Mach number, and altitude (based on the ambient pressure). In the classical FADS design, there are five orifices arranged in a cross, with one orifice in its centre. Moreover, the rigid tip will house several coaxial thermocouples to measure heat flux as well as thermocouples at the backside of the tip, which shall measure the temperature of the tip structure.

The Inflatable Heat Shield will contain several sets of sensors, representing various measurement techniques for pressure, temperature, and strain. Starting from the centre outside, there will be:

Figure 3. Sensor positioning on the windward side of the capsule

- 4 packages of flexible strain gauges integrated into the fabric, and arranged in a rosette configuration. They will be accompanied by temperature sensors for the thermal compensation.
- 12 packages of pressure and temperature sensors, mounted on the internal inflatable structure and measuring the inflow gas state through orifices in the FTPS. The pressure sensors can be also used as an extended version of FADS; this possibility requires further investigation into the influence of the Inflatable Heat Shield deformation, caused by the dynamic pressure of the inflow, on the accuracy of the extended system.
- 3 strands of the fibre-optic sensors (FOS), each containing 10 gratings (measurement points); every strand will measure different physical quantities: low-range temperature, high-range temperature, and strain.

Figure 4. Cross-section of the IHS with sensor positioning

The mounting point for all sensors at the IHS, both measuring the state of the IS as well as the ones measuring the inflow gas conditions, will be located on the Inflatable Structure, as the easier one to attach a sensor to.

An important factor taken into consideration during the design of the system is the determination of the required sensor measurement ranges and maximum allowable pressure and temperature. For ICARUS, the HMS overall design and architecture shall be suitable for both ballistic flight test conditions and real orbital re-entry conditions; however the exact sensors may be subject to change between the various conditions. This consideration is especially relevant to the frontside of the capsule, since it is exposed to the highest aerodynamic and aero-thermal loads.

Regarding the maximum pressure and temperature the sensors can withstand, it will be handled by the adjustment of the TPS between the both aforementioned conditions. For the IHS, this matter will be handled by increasing the FTPS thickness to maintain the same baseline temperature of the Inflatable Structure (i.e. the attachment surface for the sensors). For the rigid steel tip, an additional layer of rigid TPS will be applied on its front. [16]

2.2.2. Capsule leeward side

The backshell of the capsule, i.e. the back side of the IHS, will contain an additional FOS strand, measuring both temperature and acceleration; regarding the latter, a feasibility study will be conducted to determine the accuracy of such sensor combination.

The backshell outer surface will have markers in the field of view of the visible spectrum cameras, which are located in the upper pedestal of the cylinder. These cameras will be used to observe the inflation process as well as dynamic influence of the

Figure 5. Sensor positioning at the backshell and at the primary structure cylinder

flow on the whole flexible structure. The markers will serve for the rebuilding and analysis of the capsule inflation applying the Digital Image Correlation. The backshell will also be monitored by infrared cameras to provide the spatial distribution of the temperature at the backshell outer surface.

Due to the amount of data produced, the cameras will store the whole video locally. This, however, requires to provide the data storage modules with impact-resistant housing; it will be similar to the impact protection used in the vehicle's Data Storage System, described more in detail in Sec. 2.3.3. The cameras are planned to be arranged into two modules, each module consisting of: two VIS cameras with overlapping fields of view and intercrossing optical axes, and one IR camera between them.

Finally, the central cylindrical structure will have several packages of sensors:

- pairs of pressure and heat flux sensors, distributed around the cylinder in 90° intervals, and along the cylinder's axis of revolution in four rows, measuring the gas and structure state at the outer surface
- pairs of temperature sensors and strain gauges, distributed identically as the pressure and heat flux sensors packages, but set off by 45°
- an IMU at the central support structure inside the cylinder, measuring position for later correlation with FADS, as well as up to four accelerometers for structure vibrations measurements
- temperature sensors in the Data Acquisition and Storage Boards for HMS house-keeping and thermal monitoring
- four sets of pressure and temperature sensors inside the cold gas generator (CGG) intermediary space called the manifold, measuring the state of the gas during and after the inflation process.

2.3. Health Monitoring System architecture

2.3.1. System architecture overview

A general overview of the proposed architecture of the HMS is depicted in Fig. 6. The data processing is performed by the Data Acquisition System (DAQ); the data are saved in the Data Storage System (DSS). Depending on the sensor type (analogue or digital), they require different interfaces between the DAQ and DSS. Analogue sensors need to have their measurement processed by analogue-digital converters (ADC), together with sensor power distribution units (PDU) building the Data Acquisition System. The processed digital measurement can be then transmitted to the Data Storage System. Conversely, the output from digital sensors does not require ADCs, but may need a change of data transfer protocol for a one compatible with the rest of the system.

In this architecture, the power management and voltage conversion is done internally in the DAQ and DSS. Then, they distribute the power to the individual sensors.

Figure 6. Health Monitoring System architecture

2.3.2. Block diagram

The block diagram of the proposed system architecture and the measurement instruments is depicted in Fig. 7. The central part of the system consists of 12 Data Acquisition Boards (DABd), grouped logically and physically into 3 Data Acquisition Boxes (DABx), and 2 Data Storage Boxes (DSBx). They form Data Acquisition System and Data Storage System, both of which are described more in detail in Sec. 2.3.3. The purpose of both systems is data collection, processing, and storage as well as power distribution to the instrumentation. The measurement devices in the diagram are grouped in the measurement regions, as described in Section 4.1.2 and 4.1.3.

Between the sensors located outside of the primary structure cylinder and CGG areas and the DAQ/DSS, and apart from the interrogator, there

will be breakout boxes (BOB) that shall facilitate easier grouping and assembly of the physical wiring. For the sake of diagram readability, they are not depicted.

In the diagram, the power supply lines are drawn in orange, and the signal lines in blue. The power supply lines of the sensors have been omitted for the sake of readability.

The HMS has been divided into six logical sensor zones, closely corresponding to the zones of interest mentioned in Sec. 2.2:

Capsule’s payload (structure cylinder)

Primarily, it houses the Data Acquisition and Storage Systems. It also contains the sensors on the outer surface and inside, as described in Sec. 2.2.2.2. These sensors do not require to be routed via the breakout boxes; instead, they will be connected directly to the corresponding DABd’s.

Camera compartment

Located at the interface between the primary structure cylinder and the service module, it houses the VIS and IR cameras, pointed at the backshell, arranged as described in Sec. 2.2.2.2. Due to the produced data quantity, the cameras will have local data storage modules, and they will not require an interface with the rest of the system apart from the power supply.

Rigid TPS (steel tip)

As described in Sec. 2.2.1, five measurement points arranged in a cross are planned. For each point, two pressure transducers are foreseen; furthermore, this part will house several thermocouples and heat flux sensors.

Cold Gas Generator

The CGG is connected to the previously mentioned manifold; this space is then connected to the actual gas bladder of the vehicle. Hence, it will contain pressure and temperature sensors.

Flexible TPS (outer frontshell)

The flexible TPS will be exposed to the gas inflow; it is planned to install pressure transducers and thermocouples on the inner side of the inflatable structure. The integration method to expose them to the inflow gas conditions will be subject to further detailed research.

Inflatable structure (inner front- and back-side)

The inflatable structure will have sensors from several partners installed: strain gauges by PGZ, fibre-optic probes by Demcon, and temperature compensation sensors by DLR.

2.3.3. Data Acquisition System

The Data Acquisition System is a modular system that consists in general of a so-called power card and several Data Acquisition Boards. The number of DABd’s depends on the measurement task. The system has been flight-proven in several sounding rocket experiments. [17, 18]

The power card is the interface to the external power supply and communication. DC/DC con-

Figure 7. Health Monitoring System block diagram

verters provide the internal power for the data acquisition cards. Interfaces to convert external signals/flags, like pulse-per-second signal or open collector circuits, are also located on the power card.

The Data Acquisition Board is divided in two main parts: the analogue front end and the digital part, and hosts an interface supporting a maximum number of 18 sensors. The front-end logic allows to measure voltage, current, resistance and bridge-based sensors in differential and Referenced Single Ended setup. Each sensor has an analogue filter and amplifier. A multiplexer routes the signals to one ADC with a maximum sampling rate of 80kS/s, both controlled by a microcontroller. A digital filter is also implemented on the microcontroller. Digital inputs of the microcontroller are used for synchronisation with the vehicle global flags and signals. A CAD model of a data acquisition board is depicted in Fig. 8. [17, 18]

Figure 8. CAD model of a Data Acquisition Board

The Data Storage System works as a data sink; up to six systems can be connected via RS422 interface with max. 912 kBaud. The hardware contains an internal DC/DC converter. The transmitted data stream is stored one by one, so no protocol or framework is needed. Maximum capacity of one DSBx is 4GB, which leads to a maximum storage time of 97 minutes. The CAD model of a DSBx is depicted in Fig. 9. [17, 18]

Figure 9. CAD model of a Data Storage Box

2.4. Requirements for the Inflatable Heat Shield sensors

Monitoring the structural health of heat shield materials is a critical aspect of the mission, especially for the inflatable and deployable structures. From the moment of deployment, the Inflatable Structure (IS) will undergo mechanical stress, while the heat shield's flexible fabrics must withstand internal temperatures reaching up to 350°C.

The Inflatable Structure of the ICARUS mission will use Aramid-based fabrics, which have a maximum strain tolerance of approximately 2% before failure, and must operate within a temperature range up to 350 °C. Regarding the strain sensors, the primary load paths are expected along radial and orthogonal directions; however, the exact load conditions remain uncertain. As a result, multi-directional strain sensing capability is essential. The optimal sensor IHS sensor must meet several criteria:

- accurate measurement of strain up to 2%
- thermal resistance up to 350 °C
- for strain sensors: high flexibility
- minimal mechanical impact
- reliable performance on deformable substrates.

3. INNOVATIVE FIBRE-BRAGG GRATING

Fibre-optics-based sensors use so called Fibre-Bragg-Grating (FBG) etched within an optical fibre. Such a grating is a series of thin lines in the fibre that reflect a wavelength of light that matches the spacing of the lines in the grating. Other wavelengths of light can simply pass through. Changing the temperature of the fibre at the position of the grating, or straining the fibre, changes the refractive index or the spacing of the pattern respectively, which in turn changes which wavelength is reflected by the grating.

By sending a wide spectrum of light into the fibre and measuring the wavelength of the reflected light, the temperature or strain at the location of the grating can be sensed.

As gratings can be custom made, multiple sensors that are each tuned to a different wavelength can be applied to a single fibre and can be measured simultaneously.

Fibre-optic-based sensors are being used extensively in areas such as the monitoring of infrastructure on ground [19], but also in applications in the space domain [20]. They have also been flown on the NASA LOFTID mission [21].

The requirements for the FBG sensors are as described in Sec. 2.4.

3.1. Baseline design

The baseline design for the fibre optic based measurement system on board of Icarus consists out of the following baseline:

- Single COTS interrogator, modified to be suited for suborbital flight.
- Total of four optical fibres for sensors, with approximately 10 sensors per fibre.
- Fibre 1: Strain sensors on the forward side of the heat shield, measuring at key strain locations and directions.
- Fibre 2: Temperature sensors co-located with each strain sensor for temperature compensation.
- Fibre 3: Temperature sensors along the forward side of the heat shield. Straight line, radially spaced.
- Fibre 4: Single or multiple axis accelerometer (to be determined), and temperature sensors along the aft side of the heat shield. Straight line, radially spaced.

Fig.10 shows schematically the expected placement of the sensors.

The sensors themselves are to be designed to ensure proper application of them on the flexible substrate is possible, and that their measurement range matches the expected ranges for strain and temperature.

The strain sensors will be designed as a small metal substrate onto which the fibre itself is fixed. The metal substrate is formed such as to mechanically convert the expected strain range (0 to 2%) of the fabric to a strain range measurable with the FBG without damaging the fibre. The metal substrate is bonded on both ends to the fabric.

The strain sensors will also have a temperature dependency, due to the changes in fibre properties with temperature. So temperature sensors will be placed close to each strain sensor to allow compensation of this effect.

The temperature sensors will be composed of a small metal element housing the FBG. The FBG will be suspended in the housing such as to decouple it from any effects of strain, while maintaining a good thermal contact to the environment. Good thermal conductivity and low thermal capacity of the sensor will be crucial to get a good measurement of the short temperature peak expected during re-entry.

The accelerometers will consist of a small metal test mass suspended in a metal enclosure. Acceleration causes the test mass to move, which causes strain on the flexures with which it is suspended. This strain is measured using an FBG. An accelerometer is intended to be flown to demonstrate the suitability of these types of sensors for aerospace

Figure 10. Current baseline for the placement of the various optical sensors on the ICARUS heat shield

applications. A typical FBG based accelerometer is shown in Fig. 11.

A flexible stainless-steel jacket is expected to be used to protect the fibre optic cables against excessive bending and potential breaking during the folding, unfolding, and inflation.

4. INNOVATIVE STRAIN GAUGES

The strain gauges mounted on the flexible Inflatable Structure must fulfil the requirements described in Sec. 2.4. While traditional strain gauges are widely used on rigid aerospace components and present minimal challenges in terms of installation and data acquisition, applying similar approaches to flexible materials is significantly more complex. Accurate strain measurement on soft, deformable surfaces requires solutions that do not compromise

Figure 11. An example of a typical FBG based accelerometer [22]

the material’s mechanical integrity or performance. [23]

In inflatable systems, sensor flexibility becomes a fundamental requirement. Conventional polyimide strain gauges, when bonded with adhesives, tend to stiffen the structure. This can result in non-uniform deformation, introducing errors in strain readings and altering the natural behaviour of the fabric. Furthermore, due to the short duration of the mission, long-term sensor performance issues—such as hysteresis from extended cyclic loading—are not currently a primary concern. [24]

4.1. Baseline design

The baseline concept of the sensors includes several hypotheses that will be explored during its development. The sensor, when placed on the Inflatable Structure (IS), will measure forces in two directions. Wires will connect the sensor to the Data Acquisition System for data collection and storage. The block diagram in Fig. 12 illustrates the overall system architecture.

Figure 12. Concept of the strain sensor system and DAQ

The sensors will be positioned on the IS surface in a cross pattern at four measurement points. Each sensor must be capable of measuring forces in all directions, as the exact distribution of forces is unknown, although it is anticipated that the majority will align with the two principal axes.

4.2. Integration techniques

Three integration solutions are under investigation, including both commercial and experimental technologies:

1. commercial polyimide strain gauges
2. 2D printed sensors using graphene-based conductive ink
3. textile-embedded sensors created with conductive yarn.

Flexible strain sensors are commonly studied in the context of wearable and biomedical applications. Among the proposed options, both printed and textile-based sensors offer significant mechanical compliance and reduce the risk of material stiffening, although each comes with specific advantages and limitations that must be carefully evaluated. The trade-offs of the aforementioned technologies is summarised in Tab.2. Schematic representation of these techniques is depicted in Fig. 13.

Figure 13. Strain gauge manufacturing concepts

4.3. Integration tests

Different substrate materials have been tested, and several suitable candidates have been identified. Among them, the Kapton-based solution remains

the most promising option. Photos from these primary investigation are shown in Fig. 14. A high-temperature strain gauge and a compatible adhesive have also been selected. A strong epoxy bond has shown good adhesion to aramid fabrics; however, it significantly increases local stiffness, which may limit the fabric's ability to bend—an important factor that must be carefully considered. Further investigations into alternative materials are currently ongoing.

(a) Strain gauge bonded on 200 g/m² aramid with ad-hoc hi-temp glue

(b) Electrical characterisation of graphene screen print strips

(c) Electrical characterisation of an embroidered silver-plated thread

Figure 14. Strain gauge manufacturing concepts

Graphene ink was deposited onto aramid fabric using a screen-printing technique. Two types of aramid substrates were tested, with fabric weights of 60 g/m² and 200 g/m², respectively. The printed conductive bands measured 150 mm in length and 3 mm in width. After deposition, the samples underwent a thermal treatment at 350 °C for two minutes to ensure proper curing and adhesion of the ink. A multilayer deposition methodology was applied to enhance conductivity and improve overall sensor performance.

The use of conductive threads through embroidery or stitching techniques involves several considerations. Silver-plated yarns are easier to handle, but they are not suitable for high-temperature applications. On the other hand, stainless steel threads offer better heat resistance but are much more difficult to work with due to their high friction, which makes the stitching process more chal-

Table 2. Strain gauge technologies trade-offs

Technique	Advantages	Disadvantages
2D Printed Graphene	Easy installation Not invasive Flexible	Prone to break if bent with low radius and not top coated Difference in resistance between different samples
Textile	Does not break if bent with low radius Highly flexible	Complex to install by machinery Possible short circuit on the surface if not coated
Polyimide	Commercially available Extensively used	Bonding layer like epoxy adds stiffness to the material Possible breaking if bended with low radius

lenging.

Further investigation is needed to identify suppliers of high-temperature conductive threads as well as the most suitable machinery for efficient processing. Additionally, in the upcoming period, available technologies for connecting and joining these materials will be examined more closely, with the goal of optimising performance and ensuring the reliability of the final product.

5. CONVENTIONAL SENSORS

The employed conventional sensors will consist of pressure transducers, thermocouples, Negative Temperature Coefficient (NTC) thermistors, Resistance Temperature Detectors (RTD), coaxial thermocouples, strain gauges, accelerometers, and an IMU; these sensors will be complemented by visible spectrum and infrared cameras.

This instrumentation has already been employed by the DLR in various project, like ROTEX-T, ATEK, STORT [17, 18, 25, 26]. Therefore, they can be considered as flight-proven heritage; however, the ICARUS flight profile will require adjustments to them as well as their calibration, software development, and on-ground qualification in wind tunnels.

5.1. Rigid steel tip sensors and Flush Air Data System

The rigid steel tip will house pressure and temperature sensors in five points, as described in Sec. 2.2.1. For every point, pressure will be measured by two different transducers for redundancy; to achieve low response time (i.e. frequency ~ 1 kHz) pressure sensors should be no more than 40 mm behind the outer surface. Temperature will be measured at the back of the steel nose, right next to the mounting of the pressure transducers; the employed thermocouples will thus measure the structure’s temperature. Furthermore, several coaxial thermocouples will be installed inside

the structure, close to the outer contact surface, to measure the total heat flux coming from the flow.

5.2. Frontside Inflatable Heat Shield sensors

The IHS will host, amongst other, conventional pressure and temperature sensors. They will be mounted on the Inflatable Structure, on the side facing the FTPS, and connected to the outer flow conditions via a small orifice, as depicted in Fig. 15. In this design, the sensors shall not move in relation to the orifice, therefore around this area, the IS and FTPS will have to be sewn together.

This sensor integration method poses several challenges such as:

- development of a technique for adhering the sensors to the Inflatable Structure
- ensuring fully fixed position of the sensors relative to the orifice
- investigating and minimising heat transfer from the FTPS over the layer-connecting seams
- development of a technique for creating of the orifice and comparison of the sensor measurements with and without the orifice

Figure 15. Pressure and temperature sensors at the FTPS/IS

The IHS instrumentation integration, both the sensor adhesion to the IS and elimination of the layers’ relative movement in the vicinity of the sensor, is currently under investigation. The aerothermal tests of the assembly are planned at the end of 2025.

5.3. Aft cylinder sensors

The central cylinder of the vehicle contains many crucial systems, including the DAQ and DSS. It is essential to monitor the thermal state of the internal components, especially electronics. It is also beneficial to place sensors at the surface of the cylinder to measure the pressure on the outside as well as strain, heat flux, and temperature at the inner wall. This may provide valuable information about the dynamic gas behaviour in the capsule's recirculation zone.

The sensors will be distributed as described in Sec. 2.2.2. In the current design, the pressure sensors are planned to be MEMS-based due to their compact size, however it may be subject to change if their measurement limits do not cover the required range. The heat flux sensors will be placed at the same measurement points, and be either coaxial thermocouples or miniature area heat flux sensors.

Similar setup will be employed for the temperature and strain gauge pair setup. In the current design, temperature will be measured by thermocouples, although usage of MEMS-based sensors is not excluded if dictated by the accommodation limitation. The strain gauges will be attached to the wall directly next to the temperature sensors; thus, the thermocouples will not only measure the structure temperature, but also compensate the strain gauges.

5.4. Camera imagery

As mentioned in Sec. 2.2.2, the capsule aft section will contain two camera modules, each housing two visible spectrum cameras and one infrared camera. The footage from them will be saved locally. Currently, there are two possible solutions for this subsystem: either every camera will have its own printed circuit board (PCB) with a microprocessor and data storage module, or the VIS cameras will have one common PCB and the IR camera its own. The former solution is preferred, because it provides redundancy for the VIS cameras. However the determining factor in this consideration is the volume of the modules and the resultant required steel impact-resistant box.

Both DIC and FADS are planned to be processed in post-flight analysis; since there is no active control of the ICARUS vehicle, moving these computation to the PFA reduces the HMS complexity, is less prone to errors, is easier in development, and thus preferable.

6. OUTLOOK

The project ICARUS is currently in the preliminary design phase. Therefore, the development of the HMS focuses on: determination of the required sensor measurement ranges on basis of CFD and

wind tunnel tests; integration and measurement tests of the innovative sensors; and preliminary development of the Digital Image Correlation subsystem and Flush Air Data System.

Regarding the wind tunnel tests, there have been several measurement campaigns planned at the Department of Supersonic and Hypersonic Technologies of the DLR in the Hypersonic Wind Tunnel H2K, which achieves Mach numbers up to 11.2 and enables rebuilding aerodynamics and aerothermodynamics in several key flight points, and Arc-heated Wind Tunnel L2K:

1. Aerothermodynamics of the capsule in H2K, already performed in February 2025. The goal of this part has been to verify the heat flux distribution at the frontshell of the capsule, derived from the temperature distribution measured with IR cameras. The results are currently being processed.
2. Aerodynamics of the capsule in H2K, planned for July-August 2025. During the campaign, pressure distribution at 13 points of the frontshell will be measured by a pressure scanner; this will also serve as dataset for the tests of FADS.
3. Aerothermodynamics and heat flux to the IHS and sensor choice verification, in L2K, planned for November-December 2025. A small (up to 100 mm) sample cross-section of the IHS will be exposed to heat fluxes expected during the ballistic flight. The material stack-up will represent the actual design stack-up of the IHS.

6.1. Conventional instrumentation

Many of the conventional sensors employed in ICARUS have been already flight-proven; their further development, design, and adjustment for the needs of the vehicle are foreseen for the later stage of the project. The current actions in terms of the conventional sensors concentrate on the far more complex subsystems: the camera setup with the Digital Image Correlation, and the Flush Air Data System. Regarding the former, several commercially available software packages can be used for DIC; it is planned to utilise two or more tools and compare the results to choose the candidate most suitable for ICARUS. As for the latter, a DLR in-house tool for FADS is planned to be developed.

6.2. Fibre-Bragg Grating

During the next phases of the project the detailed designs of the strain, temperature, and accelerometer sensors will have to be worked out. Prototypes will be manufactured, and their application onto the fabric will be tested. Specifically off-nominal cases, such as double curved surfaces, off-

axis strain, and shear loading will need to be tested for.

The optical sensors will be included in the various (plasma) wind tunnel tests within the ICARUS project to determine their behaviour at the extreme environments of the flight, and to calibrate their output to external sensors.

6.3. Strain gauges

Subsequent prototypes and tests will be implemented, in order to understand which is the most suitable manufacturing method for the innovative sensors for the intended use. To achieve this, attempts at reduction or mitigation of the disadvantages of every mentioned sensor integration technique will be undertaken. During the prototyping phase, tests will be carried out to understand what the gauge factor of every sensor is, if there is a hysteresis, and what are the acceptable bending radii of the sensors.

Moreover, the top coating for the printed sensor will be evaluated; this could reduce breakages, and thereby the hysteresis caused by the bending of the fabric, as demonstrated by the tests performed with a vinyl and polyurethane coating.

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<https://www.he-icarus-project.eu/>
<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134997>

Figure 16. ICARUS project logo

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